

THE FINANCIAL BUDGET OF HIGHER EDUCATION – REFERENCE TO SITUATION IN ISRAEL

Alon MENIN, PhD

Ariel University, College of Management and Finance studies, Israel

alonmenin@gmail.com

ORCID 0000-0002-8163-3752

Abstract: Budgetary financing of higher education underwent many changes in the last twenty years. We are witnessing the changes and transformations that have already begun the emergence of the Bologna reforms. Because of global changes, "ups and downs" of the economic situation - Employment - and demographic changes occurred in the national priorities of the countries, and the location of the higher education national priorities decreased in every country. This means a decrease in funding, and the transfer of responsibility for funding and financial maintenance academic organizations. How the world deals with the challenge? Is there any recommended models and principles to hold the Academy capabilities with high-quality teaching and research? The article briefly displays model and operating principles are based Council for Higher Education's annual funding Israeli academic institutions.

Key words: Higher education, Bologna process, sources of financing, tuition.

BUGETUL FINANCIAR AL ÎNVĂȚĂMÂNTULUI SUPERIOR – REFERINȚĂ LA SITUAȚIA DIN ISRAEL

Alon MENIN, doctor în economie

Ariel University, College of Management and Finance studies, Israel

alonmenin@gmail.com

ORCID 0000-0002-8163-3752

Rezumat: Finanțarea bugetară a învățământului superior a suferit multe modificări în ultimii douăzeci de ani. Suntem martorii schimbărilor și transformărilor care au început deja apariția reformelor de la Bologna. Datorită schimbărilor globale, „suișuri și coborâșuri” ale situației economice, ocuparea forței de muncă și schimbări demografice au avut loc în prioritățile naționale ale țărilor, iar amplasarea priorităților naționale de învățământ superior a scăzut în fiecare țară. Aceasta înseamnă o scădere a finanțării și transferul de responsabilitate pentru finanțare și întreținerea financiară a organizațiilor academice. Cum se confruntă lumea cu această provocare? Există modele și principii

recomandate pentru a menține capacitățile academice cu predare și cercetare de înaltă calitate? Articolul prezintă pe scurt modelul și principiile de lucru pe care se bazează finanțarea anuală a instituțiilor de învățământ israeliene de către Consiliul pentru învățământul superior.

Cuvinte cheie: *învățământul superior, procesul Bologna, surse de finanțare, școlarizare.*

1. Introduction

The Higher education headed for a period of profound changes. Universities compete with each other for funding, the outstanding students, the faculty, the academic ranking, research budgets and financing, the support of private and public entities. However, they also cooperate in research and teaching for the benefit of all parties [1].

Large complex systems in higher education around the world are currently operating pressures and whirlpool big changes. Pressures emanating from different sources trying to push a restructuring of higher education and meaningful content [6]. Today, they expect universities to let accountable and act transparently towards the government and the society around. They should be revealing an entrepreneurial spirit in search of funding are different, they learn a greater number of students with varied backgrounds and different abilities, will integrate information and communication technologies news, be responsive to changes in the political and social, and of course respond to them [8]. Some changes are increasing the horizontal and vertical diversification in higher education, while others aimed to change these patterns. We find ourselves treated like the arch of variables: the overall structure - organizational relationships between the private and public sectors, admission policies, curricula, funding patterns, teaching and research policy, academic culture, evaluation and certification, and so on. Some of the changes that have occurred in recent decades have been at the international level, some at the national level in each country, and others at the institutional level within the institutions [5].

2. Main materials

The European reform - the Bologna process. The Bologna reform began on September 18, 1988, which gathered hundreds of participants from Europe and other places around the world at the University of Bologna, noted the 900 anniversary of the founding. European governments asked to recognize the contribution of the academic world to formulate ideas that led to the integration of national cultures to create a harmonious European world, and to establish bridges

between West and East Europe. One of the most important results of this conference was the formulation of "**Magna Carta Universitatum**" signed by 430 governors, directors and presidents from all over Europe [4]. Which champions the importance of preserving the autonomy to universities and protecting the academic freedom of faculty members, as well as the crucial role they play any significant social change [4].

This festive event discussed many important issues related to academic excellence, the relationship between the university, society and industry, globalization, and the roles played by the academic world, social and political changes, and many schemes been proposed to expand cooperation, successfully implemented in the coming years. One of the most successful projects was the Erasmus project, the flagship of European cooperation in the nineties of the 20th century, a project promoted student exchanges between European universities expanding scale, on the order of thousands [12]. The absorptive capacity of the Erasmus project were based on commitment professors from European countries who have agreed to provide courses and evaluation of courses compared to their counterparts in other countries and differentiate instruction so that students can enjoy learning with their students [12].

A year after the **Sorbonne Declaration** published, the Italian education minister proposed to hold a similar event in Bologna in June 1999. Many delegates from universities in 29 European countries participated in the event. Bologna Declaration expanded Bill of Sorbonne. On 19 June 1999, representatives of 29 countries were sign on the **Bologna Declaration** and launched an intensive process for the establishment of a unified European area of higher education or coordinated by the year 2010. In one of these gatherings of leaders of the Bologna process, in Berlin in 2003, already signed the on the Bologna Declaration about - 40 countries [7].

Many higher education systems in Central and Eastern Europe based for centuries, the structure of the five-year degree (master's equivalent). They did not allow undergraduate studies. Prolonged studies led to, among other things, high "drop-out" rate during the school year. Although many countries in Europe are still allowed studies with no tuition fees [3].

"**Restructuring**" of academic degrees led to profound changes in many countries. The establishment of a European System for Evaluation of Degrees and Academic Courses (European Credit Transfer System) consumption creating benchmarks for comparing the academic curriculum, and setting evaluation criteria and learning products [3]. Cooperation in setting quality standards strengthens the

transparency of academic programs and structures, and contributes to creating trust between academics in different countries throughout Europe.

To Expanding access for higher education. In recent decades, we have witnessed accelerated further discussion of access to higher education worldwide. The most radical changes occurred in the last ten years in Europe and other continents. Except for a few exceptions, such as Germany and France, participation in higher education has increased since 1995 in all European countries. The most impressive growth was Eastern and Central Europe. Nevertheless, this process has moderated recently. The expansion of higher education been linked to changes in the age of the students, acceptance criteria, the blossoming of new types of institutions, public and private [9].

Diversifying sources of financing. Copying allocation to finance the higher education of the public sector to the private sector reflects the most significant change in terms of restructuring of the institutions and the field of education. Convergence towards an integrated financial system (public sector and private sector) and of course how to change the proceeds of public sector intervention in higher education are some of the consequences that have occurred in the education of higher learning. **Governments around the world are cutting budgets, more and more, from higher education institutions, and encourage them to take initiatives and to raise their own funds in their operating budget [1].** It has a great influence on the activities of universities and status. Generous donations and grants to the world of private business and many prestigious universities in the US are a unique phenomenon in the United States [15]. **Governments fund most of the world's higher education systems.** University ideas can be entrepreneurial getting to Europe in the late nineties, when many institutions have tried to lead innovation in their management and organization of the teaching system, and be very involved in cooperation programs with industry and the world of work as a whole.

It is associated with the success of the expansion of higher education. The unprecedented increase in the number of students challenged traditional modes of financing. In light of the overall decline, prevalent in most countries, the allocation of funds to social affairs, many countries have tried to curb the expansion of public funding of education in general and higher education in particular. Today expect higher education institutions to do more, for less

The cost of a student in relation to per capita gross national product declined in most developed countries. Between 1995 and 1998, all members of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development OECD except Italy and Greece, there was an increase in expenditure per student, per capita income was

high [5]. Private spending for higher education has risen by 17 member countries of the OECD, sometimes greatly. This expense declined significantly in only three countries: *Mexico, Austria and the Czech Republic* [11].

Achieve through the resource growth of private higher education:

1. The establishment or expansion of private institutions funded, in whole or in part.
2. Payments students and their families.
3. By mobilizing new resources in the business sector.

The Funding of higher education today based, to an increasing extent, the sources involved, and students are required to pay a greater share of the costs of their training. **In most countries, not including tuition started to charge tuition fees.** Countries that would have tuition is increased. Because of the decline in public funding, **institutions forced themselves to find new resources or develop those that been neglected.** Until the eighties became clear distinction between countries, which have claimed for tuition at higher education, institutions and countries have had a free school principle. The western and northern Europe, the only payment required of the students were of a social nature or managers (registration fees, examination fees, dues to associations and sports clubs) or payments for specific services that are not included in education services [16].

Tuition - Is it right to demand it? Many countries have begun to address the question of tuition taboo. Tuition is growing in many European countries, especially *Spain, the Netherlands, Ireland* in the eighties; And in the nineties - *Portugal, Italy, the UK, Austria* and most countries in Central and *Eastern Europe* [7].

Most countries in Central and Eastern Europe hold a mixed system in which the government offers a certain number of state-funded places in public institutions of higher education. These places kept for the best students, while others must pay tuition. Outside Europe, raised tuition in most Latin American countries, India and China.

In some countries, the introduction of graduated tuition fees for different types of students. In some states of *Germany*, registered university students who stay after school period average must pay tuition, 500 euros semester. In many countries, **foreign students are required to pay full tuition**, foreign example [2].

Most countries in Central and *Eastern Europe* hold a mixed system, in which the government offers a certain number of state-funded places in public institutions of higher education. These places kept for good students. Others must pay tuition. At the same time, private institutions, whose existence depends on their income from tuition charge it [16]. *Australian* universities allowed enrolling

foreign students beyond the number of places funded by the government, and charging them full tuition. In many countries the culture program grants and loans to students, which must need them more than ever before, with an increase in tuition.

Sales of services - an important economic educational institution. Sales of services, such related activities, such educational institutions and unrelated, represents an increasing extent some of the resources. North American universities, private and public, is selling 20% of the resources. Universities are increasingly discovering entrepreneurial spirit, diversify their funding sources and reduce dependence on government. They have established new institutions designed to mediate among economic and social environment. These entities are professionally managed, commercial logic similar to that of the companies with which they come into contact. It was their duty to market the products of research and technology activities translate or experimental to practical applications [15].

Universities achieve export resources through educational programs. In addition to the registration of foreign students, many universities in *America*, *Britain* and *Australia* are opening branches in *Asia and Eastern* and Central Europe. So do the other countries with programs that have great demand. Other resources inheritances based on income, grants and donations [10].

Private education. In many countries in Asia and Latin America established private education, especially in sectors sought their costs low. In some countries, mainly the US and Europe, private higher education has been established, financially strong and competitor quality of public higher education, but in many other countries private education operates primarily motivated by profit. Often criticized the quality of the education system is flawed private offers [8].

While there is widespread recognition that institutions must put up with the socio-economic situation in the functioning of higher education, but also expressed concern about the withdrawal from the agenda of social democratization of access to higher education. This concern also raised in the context of a reference for higher education qualification "non-negotiable". Whether products and knowledge created at universities, where they are "public property" and "property-negotiable" is today an issue that arouses heated debates in many systems, and will affect the status of higher education institutions in many different countries.

Financing with foreign students. Students has treated as consumers and customers. Universities were force to sell themselves to the domestic and international - a trend that encourages horizontal diversification (the distinction between elite and institutions as opposed to less prestigious institutions) and

vertical diversification (the existence of institutions that meet the needs of students of different audiences) [1].

Transnational education also has a negative side. Many unauthorized suppliers of education are working today in many countries, for profit. They are not under the control and supervision, external or internal, and activity remains outside the official guidelines for quality assurance. Many of these institutions are "degree factories" that provide low quality education. Some argue that multi-national suppliers enjoy an unfair advantage compared to local suppliers, who lose income because they are subject to strict regulation. It is very likely that education out-nationals will expand in the future and will accelerate competition between higher education providers. Education authorities in each country and international organizations devote greater attention to monitoring and to set appropriate regulations for quality assurance, to maintain the high level of education given to multinational suppliers, but also ensure that traditional values [6].

And the future? Models for funding higher education system in the world. Other countries employ different models for financing higher education. Foremost among them are the American model and the British model. Israeli model currently used is determined according to the previously ruled England. Many of the differences between the models, as described below. These guiding principles derive British model is based on the principle of academic freedom, which public funding for academic institutions receive a budgetary one (block grant) and the University allocates the funds as it sees fit. This is in contrast to the US model allows higher education institutions to specialize in teaching or research; so using Hierarchical multi-layers: the top tier is specialized in research, teaching other academic and professional training lower. The California differs from the British model also financial incentives: a significant component of the budget of the academic units and researchers' wages derive competitive funds in order to encourage quality research. The main disadvantage of the US model against the other methods is its relatively high costs.[8]

The Israel's education budget. The rapid expansion of higher education in Israel is the result of the opening of colleges and increasing accessibility to the public. However, this process, together with the erosion of real financial resources require policy makers to increase the budget for higher education and introduce substantial changes in allocation, to improve teaching and research outputs, and to keep Israel's relative advantage. It examines the economic literature over ten years of effective ways to finance higher education [1].

3. Recommends

The economic literature suggests several principles for effective budgeting of higher education should be implemented in Israel, to [13]:

A. **Funding research:** the study has a budget of two complementary sources - one funding the basic research infrastructure (based on the outputs of the study), and the other establishing a direct link between the allocation of funds and the various academic units and research scope and quality. This intended to encourage staff to improve the quality of research and teaching.

B. **Budgeting instruction:** teaching budgeting should be simple and should reflect the real costs of teaching and teaching quality. Teaching costs divided between frontal teaching and laboratory studies. Most of the cost is due to frontal teaching, even in professions that require experimentation. It is there for recommended budget academic units at cost frontal teaching, with an additional laboratory studies. It is also recommends to link the funding of teaching quality by doing surveys on the success of graduates in the job market certain period after graduation.

C. **Priorities:** budgeting model should reflect the national priorities of the country, by strengthening the research areas in which Israel has a comparative advantage (eg applied sciences) and those that are specific to the Jewish people (Hebrew language and literature, history of Israel, etc.).

D. **Competition:** It is recommend for increase the competition among all institutions of the state budget. However by applying a uniform model for universities and colleges, and by allowing for mobility of students between institutions during their studies. The need to improve the information available to candidates to study - the quality of teaching and research institutions, the average salary of graduates of the first placement and more.

Budget principles of higher education in Israel - in accordance with the decision of the Council for Higher Education of the Ministry of Education [14]

There are a few rules and criteria for funding manipulated in any budgeting models developed by the Council of Higher Education were and remain unique landscape of public financing in Israel. It is important to note the two principles of budgeting:

Budgeting according to "outputs" - Israel was the first country in the world to fund higher education institutions. It was according to a model that based on the **output of its teaching and research institutions** in general and not directly according to the inputs invested in teaching and research. This method allows for effective monitoring events remotely managed by institutions unattended daily. Moreover, it allows diversity among institutions since every institution can select

which output of concentrate depending on the nature and specific objectives, while constantly boost efficiency and increase productivity.

The global grant - the largest part of the annual public budget is award to a global sum, without breakdown by sections of the budget, its utilization in accordance with the institution's sole discretion subject to the full budget report at the end of the year. Also appearing in the higher education budget in the state budget contains a small number of subsections and is essentially the number one. These words reflect the fact that while the volume of public funding for higher education set by the government and it has nothing to say about the system targets medium and long term, considering the needs of society and the state.

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